

New Bulgarian Resources for Studying Deception and Detecting Disinformation

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Abstract

Automatically detecting disinformation is an important Natural Language Processing (NLP) task whose results can assist journalists and the general public. The European Commission defines “disinformation” as “false or misleading content that is spread with an intention to deceive”. Deception and thus disinformation can be identified by the presence of (psycho)linguistic markers, but some lower-resourced languages (e.g. Bulgarian) lack sufficient linguistic and psycholinguistic research on this topic, lists of such markers and suitable datasets. This article introduces the first ever resources for studying and detecting deception and disinformation in Bulgarian (some of which can be adapted to other languages). The resources can benefit linguists, psycholinguists and NLP researchers, are accessible on Zenodo (subject to legal conditions) and include: 1) an extended hierarchical classification of linguistic markers signalling deception; 2) lists of Bulgarian expressions for recognizing some of the linguistic markers; 3) four large Bulgarian social media datasets on topics related to deception, not fact-checked, but automatically annotated with the markers; 4) Python scripts to automatically collect, clean, anonymize, and annotate new Bulgarian texts. The datasets can be used to build machine learning methods or study potential deception. The article describes the methods of collecting and processing the datasets and linguistic markers, and presents some statistics.

Keywords: datasets, resources, disinformation, deception, Bulgarian

1. Introduction

Nowadays, detecting untrue content becomes an increasingly important task for the general public, journalists, and Natural Language Processing (NLP) researchers. Untrue textual content includes texts written by humans with the intention to mislead or unknowingly spread untrue statements, as well as automatically generated false texts commonly known as “textual deepfakes”. Although there has been considerable research on detecting untrue (also called “fake”) texts in English (e.g. Pérez-Rosas et al., 2017; Alam et al., 2021), significantly less attention has been given to other languages, particularly the under-resourced ones. One specific type of untrue texts, written by humans, is *disinformation*. The Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions on the European Democracy Action Plan¹ defines *disinformation* as “false or misleading content that is spread *with an intention to deceive* or secure economic or political gain and which may cause public harm”. This *intention to deceive* distinguishes disinformation from misinformation (unintentionally spread false information) and makes it a type of deception. Recent existing NLP research on disinformation does not take into consideration the intention to deceive, but only the fakeness of the texts and the potential harm they may cause (Alam et al., 2021). The fakeness of the text is determined most often on the basis of comparison with fact-checked claims, stored in special international or local websites and databases, or

by comparing the text’s claims with specific ontologies. However, untrue statements that are not covered by fact-checking databases or that cannot be checked against existing ontologies (for example if such ontologies do not exist) may remain undetected. One alternative method to identify untrue statements is to recognize textual disinformation by the specific linguistic markers of deception it may contain.

While there is a lot of research on the linguistic and psycholinguistic characteristics of deceitful language (e.g. Zhou et al., 2004; Vrij, 2000), most of it is about English. There are also NLP methods using linguistic and psycholinguistic features, among many others, to detect fake content (e.g. Pérez-Rosas et al., 2017). Most often (Pérez-Rosas et al., 2017; Shrestha et al., 2020) such features are taken from the Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC²) dictionaries and tools, which are available for a limited number of languages and do not include Bulgarian. Additionally, the most recent LIWC versions are not available for free.

This article addresses several gaps in Bulgarian, such as the absence of deception, disinformation, and textual deepfakes datasets, and of linguistic and psycholinguistic resources and studies on the Bulgarian markers of deception. It also contributes to the very limited research on the language of deceit in Bulgarian (Kitanova, 2019). While the messages included in these datasets have not been fact-checked, they are a much larger alternative (over 118,000

¹<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2020:790:FIN&qid=1607079>

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² <https://www.liwc.app/>.

messages) to the existing Bulgarian social media datasets for detecting fake texts. The latter (Nakov et al., 2021) currently contain up to 3,700 messages, with very few of them annotated as containing fake information.

The present version of the new resources includes: 1) an extended (mostly language-independent) hierarchical classification of linguistic markers of deception, with three markers that may signal deepfake texts; 2) 38 thematically divided lists with a total of 618 Bulgarian expressions for matching some of the marker categories in texts; 3) four social media datasets (three from Twitter and one from Telegram) consisting of 118,570 messages mostly on the topics of Covid-19 and deception, not fact-checked, but automatically annotated with marker categories and expression lists; and 4) over 20 well-documented Python scripts for annotating other Bulgarian datasets. The social media datasets were collected via keywords search (from Twitter) and from public groups and channels on specific topics (from Telegram). Some of the keywords were taken from famous controversial Bulgarian cases involving accusations of deception, and the messages collected in this way can thus be used for linguistic studies of social media texts on these topics. The resources could also have contributions for other languages - the expression lists could be translated, and the hierarchical classification and Python scripts could be applied to other datasets parsed with the Python packages *CLASSLA*³ or *Stanza*⁴ after language-specific adaptations. The next sections provide details about: the related research on fake content and deception detection in Bulgarian and other languages (Section 2), the linguistic markers of deception (Section 3), the methods of collection, preprocessing, and statistics of the social media datasets (Section 4), and the Python scripts (Section 5). Section 6 explains the legal restrictions of access to the resources, Section 7 discusses their limitations, and Section 8 provides the conclusions.

2. Related work

Since this article concerns detecting disinformation as a type of deception, the research works most closely related to ours are Bulgarian-language datasets on the topic of fake text detection, as well as datasets and language resources (such as word lists and lexicons) in other languages that were developed for detecting deception. While there are other important topics related to the detection of fake content, such as propaganda, bias, and framing, the definitions of these terms only partially overlap with the European Commission's definition of "disinformation". As they are not directly relevant to the focus of this article, they will not be discussed in this section.

The existing Bulgarian-language social media datasets that were built for detecting fake texts include the Twitter datasets from the 2021 Workshop on NLP for Internet Freedom (NLP4IF)⁵ of approximately 3700 tweets (with very few of them annotated as "fake"), which completely

overlap with the CLEF2021 CheckThat! Lab dataset (Nakov et al., 2021) and mostly with the CLEF2022 CheckThat! Lab dataset⁶. Additionally, there is the PHEME⁷ project dataset that focused on rumours about the Bulgarian bank crisis, which includes 952 tweets. Apart from these, there are two news article datasets - the first includes 481 news articles that were annotated for toxicity (Dinkov et al., 2019), and the second includes almost 12,300 news articles, out of which 6,382 are fake stories (Hardalov et al., 2016). However, neither of these datasets is annotated with linguistic markers of deception.

There are deception detection datasets (frequently multimodal) for several languages, including English (Pérez-Rosas et al., 2015, de Ruiter and Kachergis, 2018), Polish (Rubikowski and Wawer, 2013), Chinese (Zhou and Sung, 2008), Italian (Fornaciari and Poesio, 2012), and Russian (Litvinova et al., 2017). These datasets contain texts collected from online games (de Ruiter and Kachergis, 2018), fake reviews (Rubikowski and Wawer, 2013), or court proceedings (Fornaciari and Poesio, 2012, Pérez-Rosas et al., 2015). Some of these datasets have the advantage of containing texts that are most likely to be truly deceptive (such as those from court proceedings). However, there is currently no such dataset available for Bulgarian, and it can be challenging to find truly deceptive texts.

Finally, there are some studies on the specific linguistic characteristics of Bulgarian fake news, including two classes of grammatical constructions (Getsov, 2018; Margova, 2022), as well as specific lexical expressions (Eftimova, 2018; Margova, 2021). However, to our knowledge, there are no other collections of linguistic markers focused on detecting deception in Bulgarian.

3. Linguistic markers signalling deception

The linguistic markers of deception have been collected on the basis of extensive literature review (Rubin et al., 2017; Ekman, 1985; Zhou et al., 2004; Addawood et al., 2019; Bond and Lee, 2005; etc.) mainly from studies on deception in English, as well as research on the linguistic characteristics of fake news in Bulgarian. There are also three language markers found to often signal texts generated by GPT-2, GPT-3,⁸ and Megatron (Xu et al., 2020) (for deepfake detection). Over 300 markers were originally collected, manually refined, and grouped into 97 fine-grained and 18 coarse-grained categories. The resulting classification, available in a .xlsx format, is somewhat similar to the one proposed by Zhou et al. (2004) and adopts some of their categories. Some (coarser-grained) categories are accompanied by possible methods of automatic detection, reflecting the characteristics of the Bulgarian language, and sometimes include a reference to specially created expression lists. The version of the datasets introduced in this article has been annotated with only a subset of the categories for three reasons: 1) some markers require NLP tools or language resources that do not exist for

³ <https://pypi.org/project/classla/>.

⁴ <https://stanfordnlp.github.io/stanza/>.

⁵ <http://www.netcopia.net/nlp4if/2021/index.html>.

⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/clef2022-checkthat>.

⁷ <https://www.pheme.eu/>.

⁸ <https://www.sigmoid.com/blogs/gpt-3-all-you-need-to-know-about-the-ai-language-model/>.

Coarse-grained category	Fine-grained categories and Word lists for look-up
1. Sentiment/emotions/affect	1.1. Negative emotions; 1.2. Positive emotions; 1.3. Lack of emotions; 1.4. Inciting fear; 1.5. Replace the polarity sign of emotions; 1.6. Attention-attracting expressions (list of)
2. Negation	Count of negative expressions
3. Vocabulary/expressivity	3.1. Lexical diversity/richness (type/token ratio; content words diversity); 3.2. Emotiveness/expressivity (Zhou et al. (2004)); 3.3. Redundancy (Zhou et al. (2004)); 3.4. Simple vocabulary
4. Perceptual information	4.1. Visual inform.; 4.2. Sounds; 4.3. Smells; 4.4. Taste; 4.5. Tactile inform.; 4.6. Physical sensations - Lists of verbs and expressions (4.1-4.6)
5. Unbalanced/Lack of perceptual information	5.1. Temporal information (list of Temporal expressions); 5.2. (List of) Spatial information; 5.3. Causation (list of Cause-effect expressions); 5.4. Numbers
6. Senseless or overbalanced text	6.1. Too many/irrelevant details; 6.2. Unnecessary connections
7. Details/specificity	7.1. Lack of details/memory; 7.2. Missing links; 7.3. Avoidance of discrediting information (also lack of details); 7.4. Lack of past details (past tense verbs)
8. Grammaticality and fluency	8.1. Coherence; 8.2. Syntax; 8.3. Ungrammatical/ linguistically incompetent
9. Length and complexity	9.1. Sentence length; 9.2. Text/message length; 9.3. Cognitive complexity; 9.4. Reticent (less talking, but also linked to fewer details)
10. Cognitive operations	List of cognitive operations verbs
11. Clarity	11.1. Ambiguity (lexical, syntactic), Unclarity; 11.2. Using expert terms; 11.3. Contradiction; 11.4. List of Generalization words (also linked to distance)
12. Nervousness (betraying emotions)	12.1. Arousal; 12.2. Nervousness/tension
13. Depersonalisation/distance (also "non-immediacy")	13.1. Self-references; 13.2. Group references; 13.3. Use of pronouns; 13.4. Passive voice (also sign of complexity); 13.5. Formal speech; 13.6. Automatic and template phrasing; 13.7. List of volitional words
14. Plausibility, credibility	Lists of words: Verbs for hesitation/doubt; Expressions for doubt, unclear quantity/content; Verbs for confidence; Expressions of confidence
15. Subjectivity	Subjectivity expressions in the word lists
16. Untypical way of writing for that specific person	Needs analysis of several messages of the same author.
17. Specific Part-of-speech	17.1. Number of verbs; 17.2. Number of Nouns and Noun Phrases; 17.3. Number of modifiers
18. Social media specific	18.1. Hashtags; 18.2. Mentions; 18.3 Links

Table 1: Coarse-grained, fine-grained categories and methods of their detection.

Bulgarian; 2) such tools or resources exist, but their quality is too low; 3) some categories of markers require a different type of data. For example, Category 16 requires several messages from the same author, whereas the current datasets contain separate messages from many different authors. Such data collection was motivated by our desire to prevent author identity reconstruction in accordance with European laws. The methods used to annotate the current datasets mostly involve calculating text length normalised counts of various linguistic elements (e.g. number of passives, adjectives, or locations) in texts processed by a syntactic parser and a Named Entity Recognizer (NER). For some categories (such as *perceptual*, *temporal*, and *spatial information*) the method includes performing an automatic look-up for specific Bulgarian expressions, contained in the specially created expression lists. These lists of expressions (e.g. verbs, synonyms of the verb “to see”, sensation expressions used for “feeling cold”, “warmth”, and different kinds of smells) have been collected by Bulgarian linguists after a search revealed that there was no existing resource containing all the necessary expressions. An additional list of “attention-attracting” expressions has also been compiled. These expressions were manually identified by a Bulgarian linguist in tweets related to Covid-19. Some examples include: “обрат” (in English: “sudden change”), “ВНИМАНИЕ, ВНИМАНИЕ” (in English: “ATTENTION, ATTENTION”), “Тревога” (in English: “Alarm”), “Важно съобщение” (in English: “Important

message”). Table 1 shows the 18 coarse-grained categories, their fine-grained subcategories, and the respective expression lists. The categories shown in **bold** are those that have been annotated in the four datasets (explanations can be found in Section 4). The final resource contains 38 lists with a total of 618 expressions.

4. Social media datasets

There are four datasets - three from Twitter (separated by topic) and one from Telegram. All the datasets have been cleaned, language-filtered, and anonymized. The Twitter datasets were collected via the Twitter API with academic access and thus cannot be used for commercial purposes. The three Twitter topics are: Covid-19, general lies and manipulation, and 17 famous Bulgarian political cases, in which politicians were accused (and sometimes proven) of lying. The tweets were collected between 1 January 2020 and 30 June 2022. Several keyword combinations in Bulgarian, mostly using Cyrillic letters, were used for each of the Twitter datasets, and are also shared with the set of resources (see Table 2 for examples).

The Telegram dataset was collected from nine public groups and channels, using the Telegram desktop version after checking the Telegram requirements in terms of data collection and dataset release. The topics are Covid-19, politics, and general news, and the time period is from 1 January 2021 to 30 June 2022.

Platform, topic	Keywords examples
Twitter topic: lies, deception, manipulation, deceivers	(лъжа OR лъжи OR лицемерие OR лъжат OR излъга OR измама OR измамници OR измами OR лъжец OR лъжци) (фалшиви OR fakenews OR невярно OR неверни OR подвеждащи OR подвеждащо OR неистини) lang:bg -is:retweet (Манипулация OR манипулира OR стъкмистика OR крие OR далавера OR далавери OR далавера) lang:bg -is:retweet"
Twitter topic: vaccinated members of Parliament; guest houses; dams	(ваксиниран депутат) OR (ваксинирани депутати) lang:bg -is:retweet (язовири премиер) OR (язовири прокуратура) OR (язовири прокуратурата) lang:bg -is:retweet (апартаментгейт OR (къща за гости) OR (къщи за гости)) lang:bg -is:retweet
Twitter topic: coronavirus, pandemic	Covid OR коронавирус OR Covid19 OR Covid-19 OR Covid_19 ... -is:reply -is:retweet (Корона OR корона OR Corona OR пандемия OR пандемията OR Spikevax OR SARS-CoV-2 OR бустерна доза) lang:bg isreply -is:retweet

Table 2: Twitter keywords examples.

All datasets were then cleaned of duplicates, and non-Bulgarian messages were removed using FastText⁹ - previously determined to be the best tool for Bulgarian language identification for our datasets (Gargova et al., 2022). Table 3 shows the final number of messages, which were left in the datasets after cleaning and language filtering. The datasets were subsequently anonymized in several automatic (with ad-hoc Python scripts) and manual review rounds to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and prevent user identities from being reconstructed. All data collection, preprocessing, and release processes were conducted in active consultations with lawyers specialised in Bulgarian and European law.

Platform, topics	Num. of soc. media msgs
Twitter - lies and manipulation (general) Time period: 1 January 2020 – 30 June 2022	32518
Twitter - 17 famous cases of suspected lies from Bulgarian media Time period: 1 January 2020 – 30 June 2022	15850
Twitter - Covid-19 Time period: 1 January 2020 – 30 June 2022	61411
Telegram Topics: Covid-19; 1 Bulgarian political party; 1 news media Time period: 1 January 2021 – 30 June 2022	8791

Table 3: Dataset details.

Finally, the datasets were automatically annotated with most of the categories (shown in **bold** in Table 1) of the markers of deception, described in Section 3, and by using the Python scripts, described in Section 5. As most categories represent counts of items, we normalized them to account for message length differences. This was achieved

by dividing the counts by the message length, which was determined by the number of words in each message. Figure 1 shows an example of a message with some of its annotations and its translation into English in a mock format. The original format of the annotated messages is horizontal, in a spreadsheet with many columns, which is thus inappropriate for this article.

In order to detect most of the annotated categories of markers, the texts were syntactically parsed with *CLASSLA*, and the named entities were annotated with the Bulgarian *CLASSLA* and *Slavic BERT*¹⁰ NERs, which produced the best, but slightly different, results. We plan to continue to update the datasets with annotations of new categories, when NLP tools of satisfactory quality appear.

The datasets are supplied with detailed information, which describes the contents of each column of values. Many of these values (e.g. message and sentence lengths, number of passives, number of specific Part-Of-Speech (POS) and Named Entities (NE) tags) can also be used for general research purposes, other than for deception detection.

Text	“Covid-19 не е особено опасна инфекция и никога не е била третирана като такава...” К. Ангелов 28.04.2021 г. English: “Covid-19 is not a particularly dangerous infection and has never been treated as such...” K. Angelov, 28.04.2021.												
Markers	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>words_message</td> <td>18</td> </tr> <tr> <td>negation_norm_count</td> <td>0,1111111111111111</td> </tr> <tr> <td>count_upos_all</td> <td>{'PROPN': 0.16666666666666666, 'ADP': 0.05555555555555555, 'NOUN': 0.11111111111111111, 'ADV': 0.11111111111111111, 'ADJ': 0.11111111111111111, 'VERB': 0.05555555555555555, 'CCONJ': 0.05555555555555555, 'AUX': 0.16666666666666666, 'DET': 0.05555555555555555, 'X': 0.0, 'PRON': 0.0, 'NUM': 0.0, 'PART': 0.11111111111111111, 'INTJ': 0.0, 'SCONJ': 0.0, 'PUNCT': 0.22222222222222222}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>passive_voice_count</td> <td>0,0769230769230769</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ner_types_count_bert</td> <td>{'PER': 0.05555555555555555, 'LOC': 0.0, 'ORG': 0.0, 'PRO': 0.05555555555555555, 'EVT': 0.0}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ner_types_count_classla</td> <td>{'PER': 0.05555555555555555, 'LOC': 0.0, 'ORG': 0.0, 'OTH': 0.0}</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	words_message	18	negation_norm_count	0,1111111111111111	count_upos_all	{'PROPN': 0.16666666666666666, 'ADP': 0.05555555555555555, 'NOUN': 0.11111111111111111, 'ADV': 0.11111111111111111, 'ADJ': 0.11111111111111111, 'VERB': 0.05555555555555555, 'CCONJ': 0.05555555555555555, 'AUX': 0.16666666666666666, 'DET': 0.05555555555555555, 'X': 0.0, 'PRON': 0.0, 'NUM': 0.0, 'PART': 0.11111111111111111, 'INTJ': 0.0, 'SCONJ': 0.0, 'PUNCT': 0.22222222222222222}	passive_voice_count	0,0769230769230769	ner_types_count_bert	{'PER': 0.05555555555555555, 'LOC': 0.0, 'ORG': 0.0, 'PRO': 0.05555555555555555, 'EVT': 0.0}	ner_types_count_classla	{'PER': 0.05555555555555555, 'LOC': 0.0, 'ORG': 0.0, 'OTH': 0.0}
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Figure 1: Example of an annotated message.

5. Python scripts

The resources also contain over twenty well-documented Python scripts, which can be used for cleaning, anonymizing, and annotating new datasets in Bulgarian with the linguistic markers, provided that the texts have been parsed with *CLASSLA*. *CLASSLA* is a fork of the Python NLP package *Stanza*, which supports 66 languages and has been adapted to Slovenian, Croatian, Serbian, Macedonian, and Bulgarian. The Python scripts can also be used to annotate datasets in other languages supported by *CLASSLA* or *Stanza*, provided that the necessary language-specific adaptations to the scripts and lists of expressions are made.

⁹ <https://fasttext.cc/docs/en/language-identification.html>.

¹⁰ <https://github.com/deeppavlov/Slavic-BERT-NER>.

6. Access to the resources and legal and ethical considerations

The resources can be accessed on the public platform Zenodo¹¹ via *restricted access*, subject to users agreeing to detailed legal conditions. The conditions are in line with the TRACES project's Data Management Plan¹² and were drafted after consultations with lawyers in accordance with several European laws (including the GDPR, the Artificial Intelligence Act, and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union). For example, the resources cannot be used for user profiling, in court proceedings, or for government surveillance. Additionally, the Twitter datasets cannot be used for commercial purposes.

Table 4 lists the Zenodo links where the resources can be found.

Resource	Link
Hierarchical classification of deception markers and expression lists	https://zenodo.org/record/7656905
Python scripts	https://zenodo.org/record/7657029
Datasets	
Twitter dataset on Famous Bulgarian Political Cases of Suspected Lies	https://zenodo.org/record/7614357
Twitter dataset on Covid-19	https://zenodo.org/record/7614247
Twitter dataset on general lies and manipulation	https://zenodo.org/record/7614318
Telegram dataset	https://zenodo.org/record/7614294

Table 4: Zenodo links to the resources.

The research described in this article follows the Ethical Code of the authors' host institution, the Big Data for Smart Society Institute (GATE)¹³.

7. Limitations

While providing several contributions, the resources introduced in this article have the following limitations:

- The linguistic markers (such as the number of passives, and adjectives) can characterise any text. Only in specific amounts and combinations, which also vary by text type, can they signal potential deception. For more information on how to use the markers to identify deception, please consult the instructions on Zenodo.
- The social media messages collected with keywords related to 'lies', 'manipulation', and famous Bulgarian cases of suspected deception may not contain deception but merely discuss such cases. To address this issue, a new version of the datasets has been created (see below for details).
- The social media messages in the datasets presented in this article have not been checked for truthfulness and

disinformation. However, a subset of the datasets was subsequently manually annotated for truthfulness and disinformation by Bulgarian journalists and will be published in future work.

- It is possible that the automatic annotations contain some errors due to the errors produced by the NLP tools used for pre-processing the datasets (*CLASSLA* and *Slavic Bert NER*). No manual evaluation of the annotations was done due to the size of the datasets.

8. Conclusions

This article presents the first version of a new set of resources that fills several gaps in different research fields (linguistics, psycholinguistics, and NLP) for Bulgarian. The resources can be used to study and automatically detect deception and disinformation in Bulgarian through linguistic and psycholinguistic markers of deception. They also provide a larger alternative to the currently existing Bulgarian social media datasets for fake news detection. Some of the resources can be adapted to other languages. The resources are released for free, but under specific legal conditions. In future work, we will publish a subset of these datasets labelled with truthfulness and disinformation by journalists, and we will continue to annotate the datasets with new categories. Additionally, the resources will be uploaded to other platforms to increase their reusability.

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¹¹ The full list of Zenodo links can be accessed on the project's website (<https://traces.gate-ai.eu/>), by searching for "TRACES" in Zenodo's search functionality, or by

contacting the first two authors.

¹² <https://traces.gate-ai.eu/?p=611>.

¹³ <https://gate-ai.eu/>.

¹⁴ <https://traces.gate-ai.eu/>.

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